

2-Fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene and its Derivatives

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The replacement of the hydroxyl group in fluorodinitrophenols by the Ullmann and Nadai reaction¹ does not appear to have been studied. In the present investigation the reaction on 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenol² has been examined. The phenol on reaction with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline provided 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene in good yield. As the latter contains a labile chlorine, it reacts smoothly with nucleophilic reagents (Table I).

Its reaction with thiourea afforded 2,2'-difluoro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide, whereas with dimethylformamide in presence of copper sulphate it yielded 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitro-*NN*-dimethylaniline, a derivative identical with that derived from its reaction with dimethylamine.

With *o*-aminophenol and *o*-phenylenediamine, 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene formed a 2,4-dinitrophenoxazine and 2,4-dinitrodihydrophenazine, respectively, identical with that obtained from similar reaction with 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene³. Thus when the reactive halogen atom has a nitro group and a halogen atom in its *ortho* positions, the cyclisation takes place by elimination of the halogen atom in preference to the nitro group^{4,5}.

2-Fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene.—A mixture of 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenol (4 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.2 g.), and diethylaniline (12 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for 7 hours. The dark mixture was treated with HCl (dil.) and then extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed well with HCl (dil.) to remove diethylaniline. On removing the ether, the oily product was heated with H₂SO₄ (conc.) on a water bath for half an hour to decompose any *p*-toluenesulphonate formed during the reaction. On dilution with water, the mixture was extracted with ether and the extract washed well with aqueous potassium carbonate to remove any 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitrophenol. The ether was removed from the extract after drying. The residue, a brownish black oil, was fractionally distilled in vacuum to furnish a yellow oil, b.p. 138-40°/2 mm. (Found: N, 12.44. C₆H₂O₂N₂ClF requires N, 12.70%).

Reaction with *NN*-Dimethylformamide.—A mixture of the preceding compound (2.2 g., 0.01 *M*), copper sulphate (1 g., 0.04 *M*), and dimethylformamide (10 ml) was refluxed with stirring for about 12 hours. On dilution with water (ca. 50 ml) a solid separated.

1. Ullmann and Nadai, *Ber.*, 1906, 41, 1870.

2. Schiemann, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1185.

3. Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2481.

4. Ullmann and Sane, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3734; Kehrman and Neil, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3108.

5. Sane and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1932, 9, 60.

On crystallisation from ethanol, the solid yielded 2-fluoro-4,6-dinitro-*NN*-dimethylamine in light brown crystals (1.8 g.), m.p. 69°. (Found: N, 18.14. $C_8H_8O_2N_2F$ requires N, 18.34%).

An identical product was obtained by allowing 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene to react with dimethylamine (Table I).

Reaction with Thiourea.—A solution of 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene in ethanol (2.2 g.), containing thiourea (1 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g.), was refluxed for 5 hours. On cooling and filtering, the residue was washed well with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish 2,2'-difluoro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide in maroon crystals (0.6 g.), m.p. 215°. (Found: S, 7.79. $C_{12}H_4O_8N_4F_2S$ requires S, 7.97%). The filtrate was concentrated to provide more of the compound (0.4 g.).

Reaction with Amines.—A mixture of 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene (0.01 *M*), an aromatic amine (0.01 *M*), sodium acetate (2 g.), and ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 hours. The product was separated and crystallised from ethanol.

A saturated ethanolic solution (10 ml) of ammonia, methylamine or dimethylamine was mixed with the fluorochlorodinitrobenzene (1 g.) and the whole was refluxed for 2 hours. The products were isolated in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE I

Amine used.	Derivative formed.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Methylamine	2-F-1-methylamino-4,6-D	128°	Dirty yellow	$C_7H_6O_2N_3F$	19.31	19.53
Dimethylamine	2-F- <i>NN</i> -dimethylamino-4,6-D	69°	Brownish yellow	$C_8H_8O_2N_3F$	18.51	18.23
Aniline	2-F-1-anilino-4,6-D	142°	Orange	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3F$	15.39	15.16
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	2-F-1- <i>p</i> -toluidino-4,6-D	150°	"	$C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_3F$	14.10	14.43
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	2-F-1- <i>m</i> -toluidino-4,6-D	120°	Red	$C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_3F$	14.28	14.43
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	2-F-1- <i>o</i> -anisidino-4,6-D	140°	Crimson-red	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5N_3F$	13.40	13.67
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	2-F-1- <i>p</i> -anisidino-4,6-D	143°	"	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5N_3F$	13.79	13.67
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	2-F-1- <i>m</i> -chloroanilino-4,6-D	129°	Dull orange	$C_{12}H_7O_4N_3ClF$	13.69	13.49
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	2-F-1- <i>p</i> -chloroanilino-4,6-D	180°	Orange-red	$C_{12}H_7O_4N_3ClF$	13.71	13.48
3,4-Dichloroaniline	2-F-1,(3,4-dichloroanilino)-4,6-D	146°	Dirty yellow	$C_{12}H_6O_4N_3Cl_2F$	12.34	12.14
Ammonia	2-F-1-amino-4,6-D	150°	"	$C_8H_8O_4N_2F$	20.64	20.89
<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	2,4-Dinitrophenoxazine	215°	Dark brown	$C_{12}H_7O_2N_2$	15.57	15.38
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	2,4-Dinitrodihydrophenazine	229°	Brownish black	$C_{12}H_7O_4N_4$	20.34	20.58

N, B, F = fluoro- and D = dinitrobenzene.

Derivatives of 2-fluoro-1-chloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene with a number of amines and their characteristics are recorded in Table I.

The authors wish to thank Dr. R. C. Mehrotra, Professor and Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for providing facilities.